

Deliverable 6.1: Plan for the exploitation, dissemination and communication of results

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Glossary and abbreviations

CS	Citizen Science
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
ECSA	European Citizen Science Association
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MOOC	Massive Open Online Course
NGO	Non-governmental Organisation
PESTEL	Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental and Legal
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats

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1. Executive Summary

This deliverable forms part of WP6 of CROPS, its aim to build awareness of the project, of its potential impacts and to disseminate knowledge regarding the projects' scientific and social achievements.

This document describes the plan for the exploitation, dissemination and communication of results and all the activities related to this. The aim is to reach a broad range of stakeholders by providing different levels of information through different communication means, tailored on the basis of stakeholder roles and interests. It defines the consortiums' strategy and concrete actions related to the communication and exploitation of results, and the presented activities contribute both to internal and external dissemination for all partners of the project.

This deliverable concludes with a list of future actions, defining a roadmap for future activities within the CROPS project – becoming a strategic document for partners in helping them establish the basis for their outputs in terms of future exploitation, multiplication and sustainability actions.

2. Introduction

2.1. Project background

CROPS aims to support the transition of citizen science from a small-scale to a Europe-wide level, moving it towards a modern, open-science approach. It will identify the most suitable citizen science initiatives for upscaling to the Europe-wide level, and in doing so will develop protocols, resources and examples of best practices for the upscaling of citizen science activities, helping practitioners to fully realise the potential impact of their activities towards the Horizon Europe's EU Missions. This support will be tailored to all different types of citizen science, and the different stakeholders that are involved and participation taken. CROPS will also help citizen science practitioners consider inclusivity, public trust and societal impact, whilst being fully aware of data interoperability requirements, sustainability issues and funding approaches when upscaling their activities. These goals will be pursued through four concurrent and interweaving activities: **(i) appraisal of existing citizen practices**, their activities and their suitability for upscaling; **(ii) creation of protocols and guidance** for the upscaling of citizen science, replicating and building on best practice that exists; **(iii) identification and guidance regarding practical considerations** such as open data sharing, sustainability, RRI and diverse funding opportunities; and **(iv) development of transnational citizen science communities**, including the establishing of societal coalitions and identification of potential citizen science champions to raise awareness of the potential of citizen science when addressing Horizon Europe EU Mission goals.

To support the overall objectives of the project and ambitions for Europe-wide impact and beyond, WP6 (Dissemination, exploitation and communication – the WP of this deliverable) will promote the exploitation and upscaling of project results and outputs through a wide range of dissemination and communication activities. The main objectives of WP6 are:

1. To engage a broad range of stakeholders with the CROPS activities and effectively communicate the results in an accessible manner;
2. To produce tailored communication and dissemination materials designed to meet the specific needs of all identified target audiences;
3. To ensure the CROPS project legacy by encouraging the uptake of key exploitable results (KERs) including within relevant networks and initiatives, in particular citizen science networks such as ECSA, and this call's sister project ScienceUs (<https://scienceus-project.eu/>).

2.2. Document scope and structure

This deliverable describes the overall strategy for activities within WP6 and outlines specific approaches to exploitation, dissemination, communication, and upscaling for the project. Throughout the deliverable, the relevant target groups are identified and where possible matched to: specific project outputs, channels the project can use, or actions the project can take. This document will be reviewed regularly throughout the project and updated as necessary. This document is organised into the following parts:

- **Introduction** – An overview of the CROPS project and the key terms used in this deliverable (exploitation, dissemination and communication);
- **Communication** – A description of initial communication activities that have occurred (including brand and logo development) and a content schedule for the first project period;
- **Dissemination** – A strategy for dissemination activities throughout the project;
- **Exploitation** – A plan for exploitation within the project that includes a description of key exploitable results and an overview of market analysis techniques to be used in CROPS;
- **Conclusions** – An outline of future actions within the project including for the iterative development of this PEDCR (plan for the exploitation, dissemination, and communication of results).

2.3. Definitions

Communication, dissemination and exploitation have different definitions and therefore different objectives, actions and methods aimed at different targets. The key terms in this deliverable describe the main differences between them, and are mapped across the timeline of CROPS reporting periods.

Table 1: Key definitions for CROPS PEDCR, adapted from European Research Executive Agency graphic (European Commission, 2023)

	Communication	Dissemination	Exploitation
Definition ¹	<i>“Communication on projects is a strategically planned process that starts at the outset of the action and continues throughout its entire lifetime, aimed at promoting the action and its results. It requires strategic and targeted</i>	<i>“The public disclosure of the results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including by scientific publications in any medium.”</i>	<i>“The utilisation of results in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities.”</i>

¹ Source: EC Research and Innovation Participant Portal Glossary/Reference Terms

	<i>measures for communicating about (i) the action and (ii) its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.”</i>		
Aim	To inform, promote and communicate activities and results	Make knowledge and results publicly available and free-of-cost	Make concrete use of results for commercial, societal and political purposes
Audience	Citizens, citizen science practitioners, interested parties and actors, and the media	Anyone who can learn and benefit from the results such as: researchers, industry, public authorities, policy makers and civil society	Anyone who can take the results forward or invest in them such as: researchers, industry, public authorities, policymakers, and civil society
Timeline	From project start until the end of the project	As soon as results and outputs become available and up to four years after the end of the project	Towards the end of the project, and beyond, as soon as exploitable results and outputs are available
Relevance in CROPS	Communication will play an important role in the CROPS project. Firstly, it will help create transnational citizen-science communities, social coalitions and a team of CS ‘champions’ to support the upscaling of citizen science. Secondly, it will help raise the profile of CROPS amongst targeted end-users, laying the foundation for future dissemination and exploitation activities.	The project’s focus will shift to dissemination in the second reporting period (M19 – M36) when project results are available. Dissemination activities will build on the networks established during the first period to share the project’s outputs as widely as possible. Dissemination activities will continue into the last period of the project, specifically targeting organisations who can make use of the results.	Exploitation activities will likely begin in the final year of the project (M24 – M36) and will continue beyond the lifetime of the project. The focus will be on the uptake of the projects results, both by members of the consortium beyond the end of the project, and by other organisations engaged through the project’s communication and dissemination activities.

3. Communication

The general goals of the communication activities of CROPS include: **i) to inform target groups** of the general objectives of the action and its progress; **ii) to develop clear messaging and engaging actions**, generating awareness and recognition; **iii) to evaluate the response of public and key, interested parties and actors** to the activities and outputs generated, and **iv) to create communication channels** that support the dissemination of results. The communication actions of CROPS will inform the target groups about the characteristics of the project and its relevance in the current educational, scientific and socioeconomic context. The communities created through the communication of CROPS will better understand the potential impact of the results, resources and knowledge created.

3.1. Project brand and logo

The CROPS branding and logo underpin the communication strategy. It helps ensure project communications fit within a consistent identity and that each individual communication action contributes to raising awareness of the project overall.

The project logo was developed iteratively over a period of two months. All partners were given a chance to provide feedback at each stage of the logo development, ensuring that the whole consortium has ownership of the final logo, and that it will be suitable and effective in all areas and contexts that CROPS works in.

Further details are included in the full CROPS brand guidelines (*Appendix 1*). The brand guidelines equip all partners in the consortium with materials to independently produce communications, allowing partners to adapt outputs to specific contexts and audiences (for example, different languages). In addition to the project logo, the brand guidelines contain:

- Primary and secondary colour palettes
- Variation and applications
 - Logo versions
 - Applications on backgrounds
 - Applications on images
- Geometries and minimum dimensions
- Typography, logo fonts, project fonts and secondary fonts
- Examples of improper use of the logo and unauthorised variations
- Visual identity
 - Digital screen application
 - Graphics and tables application
 - Iconographic style

The brand guidelines will be applied across all CROPS communication channels and activities.

3.2. Target groups

CROPS adopts a broad communication strategy with the aim to engage as many relevant target groups as possible with the project. This is especially important, as it will be necessary to engage citizen science projects and organisations who are not necessarily engaged with the EU Missions or their objectives more generally. Communication materials will be adapted to different target groups based on the aims of the communication and the channel being used. To help tailor communication materials, the target audiences for the CROPS project are defined in Table 2 below.

Table 2: Target groups for CROPS communication actions.

Target group	Description	Communication purpose
Citizen science projects, stakeholders and communities	Citizen science coordinators, researchers and networks, societal actors	To engage key players involved in citizen science with the CROPS approach. To present the benefits of CROPS in ensuring their activities fully realise their upscaling potential.

EU mission and transnational networks	EU mission projects, open data repositories, shared transnational resources e.g. BENCHMARKS, ILIAD, ProBleu, EMODnet, PPSR-Core	To learn from existing EU mission initiatives, open data repositories and other resources in terms of their requirements and challenges.
Academia	Academic and research institutions, especially focused on citizen science and the EU missions	To inform about project processes and outcomes. To connect researchers to the activities carried out towards the mission objectives.
Large-scale initiatives and programmes	Regional, national, EU and global; endorsed and established e.g. ECSA, ObservingTogether, EOSC	To sustain CROPS resources and findings beyond the project lifetime. To identify suitable partners for citizen science activities.
Wider citizen science community, policy makers, media	Local SMEs and businesses, cultural groups and societies, services related to the EU missions	To present the benefits of the CROPS approach in terms of engaging communities in citizen science and increasing its awareness, ultimately resulting in more inclusive and democratic policy and practical solutions.

3.3. Communication channels

The CROPS project will communicate across a wide number of channels to reach all target audiences. Communication materials will be tailored to each channel although the same content will often be shared across multiple channels. An overview of communication channels is given in Table 3 below.

Table 3: Description of communication channels used in CROPS.

Channel	Audience	Description
Website (including MOOC and transnational spaces)	All target groups	To inform on project updates, recruitment of participants for working groups and communities, sharing of resources and guidance, promotion of shared online spaces (www.crops-cs.eu).
Social media		To inform on project updates, recruitment of participants for working groups and communities, sharing of resources and guidance, promotion of shared online spaces through social media. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LinkedIn: cropsCS (https://www.linkedin.com/company/crops/cs/) • X (Twitter): cropsCS (https://twitter.com/cropsCS/) • Instagram: @cropsCS (https://www.instagram.com/crops/cs/) • Facebook: crops CS (https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=61556787060825) • TikTok: cropsCS (https://www.tiktok.com/@crops/cs?_t=8koQjSvM7cm&_r=1) • YouTube: cropsCS (https://www.youtube.com/@cropsCS)
Project newsletters		To inform on project updates; created as part of WP6 and disseminated through the website and social media channels.

Press releases	To promote the projects outputs: timed at project kick-off, mid-term and end, and before societal coalition events.
Multimedia material	To enhance knowledge of the issues and subjects related to the EU missions and citizen sciences' potential, with materials targeted at each stakeholder.

3.4. Communication strategy

With the project's communication channels and target groups defined, the remainder of the CROPS communication strategy focuses on ensuring that all communication actions are scheduled appropriately within the project timeline and are tailored to fit the intended audiences and channel. Regular work package meetings will be held that include a review of the communication strategy, and to engage all partners in communicating information about the project.

As the project's identity is further developed and recognisable, additional material will be added to the CROPS brand guidance. For instance, defining the project's key messages and corresponding target groups and channels for each of these key messages. This will involve tailoring specific social media posts, hashtags and imagery suitable for different platforms that partners can use to ensure a coherent, standardised message. Additional communication channels and actions might be considered if they are identified as bringing sufficient added value to the project.

3.4.1. Communication actions

To help plan for the regular design and creation of communication materials, an initial timetable of communication actions has been created (Table 4). This plan does not include social media posts and updates, or website communications – which will occur regularly (weekly to monthly) across the duration of the project. The plan of actions will be reviewed and updated iteratively throughout the project, informed by work package discussions and feedback from target groups, to ensure that outputs are in line with CROPS communication KPIs (see section 3.4.2).

Table 4: An initial timetable of communication activities in CROPS

Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4 project newsletters, 1 coinciding with the launch of the Special Interest Group (SIG) in upscaling citizen science (WP5). • 2 multimedia products, sharing the aims and objectives of the project. • 2 press releases, 1 for project launch and 1 to promote SIG and meetings. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4 project newsletters, plus 1 to coincide with societal coalition workshop (WP5), and 1 to update on SIG actions. • 4 multimedia products, sharing both conceptual and methodological developments, and actions of the societal coalition workshops and SIG. • 3 press releases, 1 to update on project progress, 1 to promote societal coalition workshop and 1 to report on SIG findings. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4 project newsletters, plus 2 to coincide with societal coalition workshops and 1 to update on SIG actions. • 4 multimedia products, sharing final findings, results, resources and outputs of the project. • 3 press releases, 1 to present the final findings and outputs of the project, 1 to present societal coalition workshop findings and 1 to report on final SIG findings.

3.4.2. Key performance indicators

To ensure that communication actions are in line with expected outputs and impacts of the project and align with the grant agreements' Description of Action (DoA), a range of key performance indicators have been defined, as shown in Table 5. These KPIs will be periodically reviewed to make sure that the project communication is developing and performing as expected, and in the case of deviation, the communication strategy is updated to reflect and address these challenges.

Table 5: CROPS communication KPIs.

Communication channel or action	KPI (to be achieved by the end of the project)
Website and CROPS MOOC (WP6)	30,000 website visits, 1000 downloads of resources, 30 new posts on the website, with 500 educators engaged by the MOOC.
Social media	1000 followers per channel (X/Twitter, Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, LinkedIn).
Project newsletters	Four per year, plus one per societal coalition workshop.
Multimedia material	Ten media products throughout the project.
Press releases	Eight: one per societal coalition workshop, and at main project milestones.
Communication through associated networks	40,000 registered users reached from specified, associated networks (for instance Fab Lab Network, European Consortium of Innovative Universities, and Tiny Forest Networks). Minimum of 5 meetings with sectorial organisations to present results.

4. Dissemination

4.1. Dissemination channels

In addition to the channels already identified for communication, several dissemination-specific channels will also be used by the project. Collaboration with related initiatives (such as the sister project ScienceUs) will be of even greater importance for dissemination than for communication as many of these initiatives are themselves targets for CROPS dissemination activities.

Table 6: Description of dissemination channels for CROPS

Channel	Audience	Description
Repositories and databases	Citizen science actors; wider citizen science community	To share the full content of all the projects screened by CROPS, and other outputs through (i) existing, established platforms (e.g., EOSC, EMODNet); and (ii) existing fora (e.g., ILIAD, GLOBE, PPSR-Core, Sci-Starter, the Zooniverse).
Scientific conferences	Citizen science actors; wider citizen science community; academia	To inform regarding project methodologies, community findings, dissemination of project outputs. Conferences include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European Citizen Science Association Conference 2024 and 2026 • Conference for the Advancement of Participatory Science 2024, 2025 and 2026 • Australian Citizen Science Conference 2025 • CitSci Africa International Conference 2025/2026
Scientific publications	Citizen science actors; wider citizen science community; academia	To inform regarding project methodologies, community findings, dissemination of project outputs. Targeted publications include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Citizen Science: Theory and Practice (Ubiquity Press) • Journal of Science Communication (SISSA Medialab) • Open Research Europe (European Commission) • PLOS ONE and subsidiaries (PLOS)
Societal coalition workshops and working group	Citizen science actors; wider citizen science community	To investigate the expressed and unexpressed potential of citizen science towards the benefit of different areas of society, to understand the state of the art of CS and society in Europe and better direct further upscaling strategies.
Special Interest Group (SIG) in upscaling citizen science	EU mission and transnational networks; large-scale initiatives; wider citizen science community	A key part of the success of the CROPS project will be collaborating with existing actions, to ensure the upscaling of citizen science is relevant both to the EU missions and to the research and innovation landscape. The SIG founding members will be the CROPS consortium, representatives of the European Citizen Science (HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-60) and IMPETUS (HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-61) projects, and the consortium of the sister project ScienceUs. In addition, current EU projects that address the Horizon Europe EU missions will be invited

		(BENCHMARKS, ProBleu, ILLIAD etc.) along with representatives of larger citizen science and EU mission groups (ECSA, Cos4Cloud, NetZeroCities).
CROPS Citizen science 'champions'	EU mission and transnational networks; wider citizen science community	CS 'champions' in public authorities, policy, civil societies, research, SMEs and industries will be recruited to 'connect the dots' between different services and institutions, and to raise awareness of citizen science and its potential at the ERA scale. Youth champions will be especially targeted, to propagate the power of citizen science amongst younger generations through the networks of European Schoolnet.

4.2. Target groups

Although in general the aim of dissemination actions is narrower than that of communication (see Table 1), due to the nature of CROPS, both in being a Coordination Support Action and involving the discipline of citizen science – all target groups are applicable for dissemination actions. This is since methodologically citizen science includes all aspects of society as its stakeholders (academia, business, policy makers, NGOs, public authorities, and large-scale networks), and therefore all need to be considered when upscaling citizen science initiatives. Subsequently, all the described target groups and their actors can benefit and learn from project results.

Further details of how these target groups will be engaged in the exploitation of project results is given in *section 5.1.1 – Market segmentation*.

4.3. Dissemination management

Dissemination will be the joint responsibility of all partners in the project consortium. Dissemination efforts will be coordinated by the work package leader, Earthwatch. To help capture all dissemination activities from each partner, a “*dissemination tracker*” has been created and is saved on the CROPS shared drive. Copies of all dissemination materials (documents, presentations and other text, audio, or video) will also be saved on the shared drive, and where possible, also made available through the project website.

4.3.1. Key performance indicators

To ensure that dissemination activities are at a sufficient level to support the expected exploitation of project result and outputs, several key performance indicators have been defined (see Table 7). These KPIs will be again periodically reviewed alongside the communication KPIs to both explore and exploit the

crossovers between them, and to identify any deviations where additional dissemination actions might be required.

Table 7: CROPS dissemination KPIs

Dissemination channel or action	KPI (To be achieved by the end of the project)
Repositories and databases	At least 7 platforms or fora.
Scientific conferences	At least 10 presentations at conferences throughout the project.
Scientific publications	At least 5 publications.
Societal coalition workshops and working group	3 online and 2 offline societal coalition workshops – involving at least 20 participants across differing stakeholder types.
Special Interest Group (SIG) in upscaling citizen science	At least 2 meetings a year for the duration of the project. SIG should involve at least 50 participants.
CROPS Citizen science ‘champions’	10 citizen science ‘champions’ identified and recruited to disseminate CROPS outputs. At least 2 champions per EU mission.

5. Exploitation

Although exploitation activities and actions will only become a focus towards the end of the CROPS project, when results and outputs are available, it can be beneficial to define a strategy at the start of the project. This will allow dissemination activities which are carried out to be targeted to suitable audiences (potential end-users of project outputs), and communication activities to involve networks that can assist with sharing exploitation activities as and when they are carried out.

An exploitation strategy requires all relevant outputs of the project to be identified. An overview of the key exploitable results (KERs) is given in Table 8 below. Further results and outputs may emerge as the project develops, and therefore this register will be updated if required. Each KER is also described in more detail in section 5.2.

Table 8: A description of anticipated exploitable results with responsible partner(s) identified

Code	Project result or output	Responsible partner(s)
KER 1	The project website, hosting all resources generated in the context of CROPS, maintained for at least seven years.	Earthwatch
KER 1.1	Database of citizen science activities suitable for upscaling to a transnational level, identified by the scalability assessment process.	Ideas for Change
KER 1.2	Recommendations, guidance and best-practice materials for the upscaling process, including user-centred design, engagement, communication and training at broader scales.	IIASA, OutBe, INOVA+ and Earthwatch
KER 1.3	Protocol and guidelines for ensuring the sustainability of upscaled citizen science, including data interoperability and diverse funding models.	Earthwatch and INOVA+
KER 1.4	Shared online spaces for transnational citizen science communities, and a citizen science 'champions' online space to promote the potential of citizen science.	OutBe and IIASA
KER 2	Fully accessible documentation of the management, reviewing, monitoring and reporting processes related to the CROPS scalability assessment methodology, which can be used as a reference by any other project which has to implement a similar screening process.	Ideas for Change
KER 3	Marketing and creative materials used to promote CROPS communities, events and outputs, which can be adapted and reused by other projects.	OutBe and Earthwatch
KER 4	CROPS Massive Open Online Course (MOOC), to enable educators and their students to fully-realise the potential of citizen science and the CROPS outputs.	EU Schoolnet

5.1. Market analysis

To ensure the results produced by the CROPS project are designed to meet the needs of a suitable target market of end-users, a number of market analysis techniques will be applied. In this deliverable, this analysis has been carried out at the level of the project. Although many of the market-analysis terms and techniques are more commonly applied to for-profit exploitation, they can provide equal value for not-for-profit models of exploitation such as sharing results among researchers and with policy makers. Whether for-profit or not, the basic principles of market analysis are to identify the group(s) of potential end-users (market segmentation), establish the benefit of the project results to these users (added-value analysis), analyse the level of competition from equivalent existing ‘products’ (SWOT and competition analysis), and consider how the uptake of the project results might be positively or negatively affected by wider trends or market drivers (PESTEL analysis).

5.1.1. Market segmentation

A generalised set of target groups is described in Table 9. This group of end-users is a sub-set of the full list of target audiences (see Section 3.3) and, for example, does not include media organisations which will be a key target audience for the project’s communication activities but are unlikely to be end-users for the project’s outputs. In the next version of this deliverable, more detailed market segmentation will be carried out for each specific KER.

Table 9: Identified end-users of CROPS KERs

Target group and description	Anticipated exploitation
Citizen science projects, stakeholders and communities: Existing citizen science projects that have the capability to upscale to the European-wide level or have already done so and can share their experiences and knowledge.	Adoption of CROPS interventions, resources and guidance to support the upscaling of existing citizen science activities. For example, projects can use the guidance on training and engaging larger audiences, or regarding data interoperability to ensure their outputs are widely exploited beyond the initial scope of the project.
EU mission and transnational networks: Larger, European-wide networks focussed on the EU mission objectives, who perhaps have yet to realise the potential of using citizen science as a methodology or the data they collect.	Adoption of the CROPS upscaling assessment process, to identify citizen science projects that have the potential to contribute to their networks and mission objectives at the transnational level. Involvement and exploitation of CROPS shared online spaces to learn more about citizen science, its societal impact and to grow their own networks.
Academia: Academic and research institutions focused on citizen science and associated with the EU missions. In particular, researchers working on behavioural science, life-cycle analysis,	Continued use of the CROPS scientific results package for further analysis or hypothesis testing. Deployment of research tools such as the shared online spaces and the CROPS scalability assessment methodology.

the environment, and public engagement.	
Large-scale initiatives and programmes: Established and endorsed regional, national and global programmes and initiatives – especially those targeted at European-wide or larger issues and those related to the 5 EU mission objectives.	Complimentary use of CROPS shared community spaces, creation of synergies regarding the promotion of CROPS guidance, resources and spaces to support the upscaling of citizen science. Adoption and endorsement of CROPS scalability assessment methodology, especially when addressing EU mission objectives. Endorsement of CROPS MOOC, to train stakeholders regarding the potential of citizen science both scientifically and for the benefit of society.
Wider citizen science community	
Public authorities and agencies: Organisations responsible for services and actions related to EU mission objectives.	Adoption of CROPS interventions to engage communities in supporting the adoption of citizen science to address societal issues. For example, training and hosting community groups, recruiting new participants to the CROPS MOOC, or distributing material and findings from the transnational shared spaces and SIG. More in-depth campaigns could also be run using the full CROPS scalability assessment methodology.
NGOs: (Environmental) NGOs actively working with communities, businesses and policy makers towards societally beneficial actions.	
Businesses: Particularly businesses with ambitions to address or contribute towards EU mission objectives through community involvement.	Supporting community-led citizen science campaigns for example by sharing material from the CROPS online resources or interactive community spaces with their customers.
Policy makers: Relevant decision makers who set policies and targets at local, national, and regional (e.g. EU) levels that have the potential to contribute towards EU mission objectives.	Use of the CROPS results (particularly the SIG findings, societal coalition working group findings, and the scalability assessment methodology) to inform EU mission policy creation and assessment.

5.1.2. Added-value analysis

To assess the added-value of each of CROPS KERs, the ‘Value Proposition Canvas’ (Osterwalder *et al.*, 2015) developed by b2bInternational will be used (Figure 1). The value proposition canvas is a tool to help make explicit how a project output delivers benefit in response to the specific ‘pains’ and ‘gains’ of the target end-user.

Figure 1: The value proposition canvas template from b2bInternational.

The value proposition canvases will be populated with insights gained from: (i) consortium meetings, discussions at external events and conferences, (ii) interaction with potential end-users in case activities, and (iii) discussions with other citizen science practitioners through ECSA, ScienceUs, IMPETUS and other networks. If needed, these assumptions about end-users' needs might also be validated through a more formal methodology such as surveys, interviews or workshops with potential end-users.

5.1.3. SWOT and competition analysis

A SWOT (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats) analysis is a common tool to identify competitive advantage (and risks of competition) for new products and businesses. CROPS prefers to frame its results in a context of collaboration (with other organisations and researchers) rather than one of competition. Nevertheless, for the outputs from the project to be successfully exploited they will need to demonstrate adequate value to end users and in some sense 'outcompete' other alternative interventions. As such, the SWOT analysis presents a useful framework to ensure that the project is able to maximise strengths and opportunities when developing project outputs whilst also identifying, and mitigating where possible, any weaknesses or threats.

An example SWOT analysis is included in Table 10 below.

Table 10: Generalised SWOT analysis for the CROPS KERS

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expertise of the consortium • In-depth insight into citizen science community and behavioural dynamics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sustainability of project outputs • Focus on EU missions could reduce scalability of citizen science activities
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaboration with sister project ScienceUs, ECSA, IMPETUS and other EU mission projects • Ongoing policy, business and community discussions around EU mission objectives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Similar outputs from sister project ScienceUs, and existing citizen science research • Unable to 'cut through the noise' within ECSA and other citizen science networks

Based on the outcomes of the SWOT analysis, further competition analysis may be undertaken, where possible focusing on opportunities for collaboration. Some illustrative examples of this kind of analysis are included in Table 11.

Table 11: Example competition and collaboration analysis (including levels of competition on a scale of low, mid and high)

Competition (from or for)	Level	Collaboration opportunities
From parallel developments (e.g. sister project ScienceUs, or other CS initiatives)	High	Good opportunities for collaboration with sister projects, especially in joint dissemination and exploitation (combined results package)
From other citizen science and EU mission platforms and networks	Mid	Existing results and resources from other platforms and networks can be incorporated into CROPS interventions to ensure that the project builds on current developments, rather than duplicating efforts. Where possible, project results will be shared with open licences to allow other projects and initiatives to similarly adopt CROPS outputs.
For the time and effort of existing citizen science projects and their wider communities	High	An opportunity to look to collaborate with other organisations already using citizen science in a community and/or EU mission context, so engagement efforts are not duplicated, and CS projects are not overburdened with separate communications.
For continued funding (public or private)	High	Collaboration with other (competing) initiatives and partners on funding bids, and opportunities such as afforded by IMPETUS.

5.1.4. PESTEL analysis

The previous steps of market analysis (market segmentation, added-value analysis, and competition analysis) can all be disrupted by changes in external market drivers. These changes can be analysed using the PESTEL framework which considers a project’s political, economic, social, technological, legal and environmental contexts. Changes in each of these contexts can affect the uptake

of project's results both positively and negatively. Often, when a potential change is first identified it can be difficult to assess whether the effect will be positive or negative as it is dependent on the exact nature of the change. As such, the PESTEL analysis will need to regularly applied throughout the project to assess the impact of context changes as their details and implications become more apparent. Table 12 shows a PESTEL analysis for the CROPS KERs.

Table 12: A project-level PESTEL analysis for CROPS, including an estimate of impacts; positive (+), negative (-), or unknown outcome (+/-)

Context	Effect	Impact
Political	Changes in relevant policy (for example, developments in the European Green Deal, or other policies building on the EU mission objectives)	+
Economic	Improvements in economic growth, interest rates and subsequent impacts on consumer behaviour and industry and government investment	+/-
Social	Societal attitudes towards citizen science (and the EU mission objectives more broadly)	+
Technological	Improved data availability regarding citizen science methodologies, from sensor technologies, data sharing platforms and other monitoring developments	+
Environmental	Continued global (mis-) management of environment to contribute towards EU mission objectives (and raises awareness and motivation for action)	+
Legal	New laws come into place which alters stakeholder behaviour (e.g. extending environmental protection laws)	+/-

5.2. Key exploitable results

KER 1 – CROPS project website

Lead partner: Earthwatch

Description: The project website, hosting all resources generated in the context of CROPS, maintained for at least seven years. This includes the outputs and resources generated by KERs 1.1 – 1.4.

Unique value proposition: A user-friendly 'one-stop shop' for all CROPS outputs and resources

Target users: Citizen science practitioners, wider CS communities, public authorities, NGOs, academia, EU mission initiatives.

Proposed development timeline:

The website will be launched in the first month of the project in parallel to developing other communication materials in T6.3 and will be periodically updated, as new resources become available. It will complement the existing information about citizen science, and the EU missions, hosted on relevant network and R&I websites.

KER 1.1 – Database of citizen science activities for upscaling

Lead partner: Ideas for Change

Description: Database of citizen science activities suitable for upscaling to a transnational level, identified by the scalability assessment process.

Unique value proposition: A database of carefully-curated citizen science projects, which have been through the CROPS scalability assessment methodology, and that address one of the five EU missions.

Target users: Citizen Science networks, EU mission networks, policy makers and public authorities.

Proposed development timeline:

Based on the inclusion criteria defined in the CROPS scalability assessment methodology, existing projects, initiatives or actions will be clustered under each of the 5 EU Missions based on their scope and impact. This mapping exercise will be the result of a collective effort from all partners to leverage the in-depth / local as well as international knowledge and experience of the discipline and its evolutions of the organizations and individuals involved in this consortium. The result will be a living, open database to which also external actors will be asked to contribute. The first version of this will be available in M18, delivered in conjunction with a Scalability Ranking Report.

KER 1.2 – Recommendations, guidance and best-practice materials

Lead partner(s): IIASA, OutBe, INOVA+ and Earthwatch

Description: Recommendations, guidance and best-practice materials for the upscaling process, including user-centred design, engagement, communication and training at broader scales.

Unique value proposition: A set of materials that build on citizen science methodologies targeted at design, engagement, communication and training, by being focussed towards the upscaling of citizen science practices, the EU mission objectives, and sustainability at the transnational level.

Target users: Citizen science practitioners, wider CS communities, citizen science networks and larger initiatives.

Proposed development timeline:

Recommendations, guidance and best-practice materials will be developed and iteratively improved through user-centred design processes throughout the duration of the project. Milestone developments will be i) CROPS communication strategies for upscaling (M24); ii) CROPS guidelines for stakeholder engagement (M26); iii) Curated training resources for upscaled citizen science (M30); and iv) User-centred design protocols for upscaling (M34).

KER 1.3 - Protocol and guidelines for ensuring sustainability

Lead partners(s): Earthwatch and INOVA+

Description: Protocol and guidelines for ensuring the sustainability of upscaled citizen science, including data interoperability and diverse funding models.

Unique value proposition: Guidance and protocols focussed towards the sustainability of citizen science activities at the transnational level, including strategies for data-sharing and interoperability, and mobilising funding.

Target users: Citizen science practitioners, wider CS communities, citizen science networks and larger initiatives, public authorities and policy makers.

Proposed development timeline:

Sustainability protocols and guidelines will be developed and iteratively improved through user-centred design processes throughout the duration of the project. Milestone developments will be i) Open data repositories analysis report (M18); ii) Mapping of citizen science funding models (M20); iii) Guidelines for citizen science data interoperability (M24); and iv) Protocol for mobilising funding and ensuring sustainability (M30).

KER 1.4 - Shared online spaces for transnational citizen science communities

Lead partner(s): OutBe and IIASA

Description: Shared online spaces for transnational citizen science communities, and a citizen science 'champions' online space to promote the potential of citizen science.

Unique value proposition: Five online communities focussed on each of the EU missions, and how citizen science activities can contribute towards them. Through these spaces, mutual learning workshops will take place to look at societal coalitions, a SIG to consider the upscaling of citizen science, and 'citizen science champions' identified to spread CROPS messages and resources.

Target users: Citizen science practitioners, wider CS communities, citizen science networks and larger initiatives, academia, public authorities and policy makers.

Proposed development timeline:

Shared online spaces and accompanying online functionality will be developed in conjunction with the iterative development of the CROPS website. This will be underpinned by the development of specific online spaces and resources provided for each Mission, and a CROPS Citizen Science Champions Page profiling each of the champions recruited. Milestone developments will be i) CROPS citizen science champions webpage (M10); ii) CROPS transnational community online spaces (M14); iii) Report on CROPS mutual learning workshops (M34); iv) Final report on societal working group findings (M35); and v) Upscaling citizen science SIG findings (M36).

KER 2 - CROPS scalability assessment methodology

Lead partner: Ideas for Change

Description: Fully accessible documentation of the management, reviewing, monitoring and reporting processes related to the CROPS scalability assessment methodology, which can be used as a reference by any other project which has to implement a similar screening process.

Unique value proposition: A methodology for scalability assessment, focussed specifically at citizen science, and incorporating a range of short- and long-term impacts, sustainability criteria, engagement strategies and relation to the EU mission objectives.

Target users: Citizen science practitioners, citizen science networks and larger initiatives, academia, public authorities and policy makers.

Proposed development timeline:

From M6 to M18 of the project, each citizen science project will be evaluated across 9 related dimensions extracted from the EU framework of Scaling and Spreading in Citizen Science. Identified projects are therefore assessed in terms of: their demonstrated impact on the EU missions (Proof of Value); the level of ease of understanding and implementation (Ease of Use and Understanding); their level of openness (in terms of open data, open software, open hardware and governance); elements related to the project's narrative and communication; the presence and usability of knowledge sharing and transfer resources; the presence of champions and boundary spanners (both locally and internationally); and the level of alignment of the original project with issues experienced across the EU as well as from a legal and social values perspective. During this process, a final version of the scalability assessment process and its criteria will be published (M12).

KER 3 - Marketing and creative materials

Lead partner(s): OutBe and Earthwatch

Description: Marketing and creative materials used to promote CROPS communities, events and outputs, which can be adapted and reused by other projects.

Unique value proposition: A set of materials targeted to facilitate the promotion, communication, dissemination and exploitation of CROPS and other resources towards the upscaling of citizen science to the transnational level.

Target users: All.

Proposed development timeline:

Targeted marketing and creative materials will be created to coincide with all of the milestones explained in KERS 1-4, with regular feedback and discussion taking place to evaluate its impact. The culmination of this process will be a full report on citizen science and its upscaling to a transnational level (M34), which will encompass all CROPS activities, outputs and impacts.

KER 4 - CROPS Massive Open Online Course (MOOC)

Lead partner: EU Schoolnet

Description: CROPS Massive Open Online Course (MOOC), to enable educators and their students to fully-realise the potential of citizen science and the CROPS outputs.

Unique value proposition: A MOOC specifically targeted to educate regarding citizen science methodology, its applicability in different contexts, and its relevance to the EU mission objectives.

Target users: Citizen Science networks, EU mission networks, policy makers and public authorities.

Proposed development timeline:

The MOOC will be linked to the Scientix STEM Discovery Campaign, taking place from February to April each year. The idea is to invite teachers to disseminate their activities and Learning Scenarios on citizen science in the campaign (developing a Learning Scenario is a requirement to pass the MOOC). This is an excellent opportunity to amplify the impact of the MOOC and promote citizen science in education. As such, the CROPS MOOC for educators and students will launch in M24 (December 2025).

6. Conclusion

This deliverable has presented a plan for the exploitation and upscaling of the CROPS key exploitable results, supported by a wide range of communication and dissemination actions. Further results or opportunities for communication are likely to arise during the lifetime of the project and, where possible, these new outputs will be incorporated into this plan.

6.1. Future actions

A number of further actions have been identified which should be implemented in the coming years and included in this deliverable.

Communication

- Further development of the CROPS brand guidelines including the definition of the project's key messages and the corresponding target audience and communication channel for each of these key messages.
- Tracking of all communication actions and iterative assessment and adjustment of these actions in line with the project's communication KPIs.

Dissemination

- Tracking of all dissemination actions and collation of all materials (including documents, presentations and other text, audio, or video) for further use.
- Mapping of all dissemination actions to target audiences and key exploitable results.

Exploitation

- Updated register of key exploitable results including details of IP rights, licensing, and corresponding dissemination activities.
- Market analysis for each key exploitable result (including KER-specific identification of end-users, added value analysis, SWOT and competition analysis and PESTEL analysis).

7. References

European Commission, European Research Executive Agency, (2023). *Communication, dissemination & exploitation what is the difference and why they all matter*, Publications Office of the European Union. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2848/289075>

Osterwalder, A., Pigneur, Y., Bernarda, G., & Smith, A. (2015). *Value Proposition Design: How to Create Products and Services Customers Want*. John Wiley & Sons.

8. Appendices

8.1. Appendix 1: CROPS branding guidelines

8.1.1. Partner Details and logos

#	Short name	Participant organisation name	Country	Logo
1	INOVA+	INOVA+ Innovation Services S.A.	Portugal	
2	Earthwatch	Conservation Education and Research Trust	UK	
3	IIASA	International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis	Austria	
4	IFC	Ideas For Change	Spain	
5	EUN	EUN Partnership AISBL (European Schoolnet)	Belgium	
6	OutBe	Outbe S.R.L. Societa Benefit	Italy	

8.1.2. Brand identity

Horizontal logo version

Version with and without the tagline.

Vertical logo version

Version with and without the tagline.

Pictogram

The pictogram should be used only where the text "crops" does not have enough space to be included (e.g., in the app icon).

8.1.3. Colours

Primary palette

The primary colors are used for all outputs both online and offline.

Violet

CMYK: 86, 80, 0, 0
RGB: 70, 63, 164
#463FA4

Green

CMYK: 35, 0, 70, 0
RGB: 175, 238, 106
#AFEE6A

Pink

CMYK: 17, 50, 0, 0
RGB: 230, 142, 243
#E68EF3

Secondary palette

The secondary colors are to be used as complementary additions to the primary palette and are primarily employed for tables, charts, icons, illustrations, etc., related to the “crops” domain.

Dark Violet

CMYK: 95, 93, 10, 0
RGB: 54, 48, 129
#363081

Dark Green

CMYK: 35, 0, 70, 20
RGB: 161, 200, 95
#A1C85F

Dark Pink

CMYK: 17, 50, 0, 20
RGB: 194, 109, 209
#C26DD1

8.1.4. Variations and applications

Logo versions

Depending on the background onto which the logo is applied, it is preferable to use different versions to ensure maximum readability.

Various cases will be illustrated subsequently.

10

Violet backgrounds

On purple backgrounds, ensuring the legibility of the logo is essential.

Therefore, the Logo-White version should be used for purple shades ranging from 50% to 100% saturation.

For shades below 40% saturation, the Logo-color version must be used.

11

Green backgrounds

On green backgrounds, ensuring the legibility of the logo is crucial.

Therefore, the Logo-color version must be used on all shades of green.

12

Pink backgrounds

On pink backgrounds, ensuring the legibility of the logo is crucial.

Therefore, the Logo-color version must be used on all shades of pink.

13

Black/Grey backgrounds

On black and gray backgrounds, ensuring the legibility of the logo is crucial.

Therefore, the Logo-White version should be used for black shades ranging from 50% to 100% saturation.

For shades below 40% saturation, the Logo-Black version must be used.

It is not possible to use the Logo-color version on black/gray backgrounds.

14

Dark colored backgrounds

On dark colored backgrounds, ensuring the legibility of the logo is crucial.

Therefore, the Logo-White version must always be used.

It is not possible to use the Logo-color version on dark colored backgrounds.

15

Light colored backgrounds

On light colored backgrounds, ensuring the legibility of the logo is crucial.

Therefore, the Logo-Color version must always be used.

16

Applications on images

To place the logo on images, the background must be uniform and not gradient, ensuring the legibility of the logo.

Therefore, depending on the background where it is to be positioned, either the Logo-color or Logo-White version should be used.

It is recommended to prioritize on images the logo version without the tagline.

Applications on images

To place the logo on images, the background must be uniform and not gradient, ensuring the legibility of the logo.

Therefore, depending on the background where it is to be positioned, either the Logo-color or Logo-White version should be used.

It is recommended to prioritize on images the logo version without the tagline.

8.1.5. Geometries, safe area and dimensions

Geometries

The golden ratio curve was followed to make logo and pictogram harmonious and well-balanced.

Geometries

It is always necessary to develop the logo within a well-designed and balanced geometry.

Safe area - horizontal version

It is always necessary to consider a safe area around the logo to prevent incorrect placement or interactions of other elements with the logo itself.

The logo is enclosed in a rectangle of 19x width and 12.5x height. No element can be inserted into the colored rectangle, which is equivalent to dimensions of 3x both in height and width.

Safe area around logo variations
-Horizontal version-

Safe area - vertical version

It is always necessary to consider a safe area around the logo to prevent incorrect placement or interactions of other elements with the logo itself.

The logo is enclosed in a rectangle of 11x width and 19.5x height. No element can be inserted into the colored rectangle, which is equivalent to dimensions of 3x both in height and width.

Safe area around logo variations
-Vertical version-

Minimum dimensions

They indicate the minimum allowable size for logo usage and aim to prevent situations of poor legibility of the logo, both for digital and print purposes.

The minimum usable size for the horizontal logo with the tagline is:

The minimum usable size for the vertical logo with the tagline is:

The minimum usable size for the horizontal logo without the tagline is:

The minimum usable size for the vertical logo without the tagline is:

8.1.6. Typography

Logo font

The fonts used for the logo are:

- Montserrat bold
- Montserrat medium

Montserrat Bold

AaBbCcDdEe123

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuwx
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUWXY
 £!@#\$\$%^&*()_+==[]0;'\,./:'|<>?

Montserrat Medium

AaBbCcDdEe123

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuwx
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUWXY
 £!@#\$\$%^&*()_+==[]0;'\,./:'|<>?

Institutional font

The institutional typeface for "crops" is:

the **Montserrat font family** (available for download from [Google Font](#))

Montserrat Thin
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 1234567890 +-=/ £\$%&(){}|![]?^*~@#

Montserrat ExtraLight
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 1234567890 +-=/ £\$%&(){}|![]?^*~@#

Montserrat Light
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 1234567890 +-=/ £\$%&(){}|![]?^*~@#

Montserrat Regular
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 1234567890 +-=/ £\$%&(){}|![]?^*~@#

Montserrat Medium
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 1234567890 +-=/ £\$%&(){}|![]?^*~@#

Montserrat SemiBold
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 1234567890 +-=/ £\$%&(){}|![]?^*~@#

Montserrat Bold
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 1234567890 +-=/ £\$%&(){}|![]?^*~@#

Montserrat ExtraBold
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 1234567890 +-=/ £\$%&(){}|![]?^*~@#

Montserrat Black
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 1234567890 +-=/ £\$%&(){}|![]?^*~@#

Montserrat Thin Italic
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 1234567890 +-=/ £\$%&(){}|![]?^*~@#

Montserrat ExtraLight Italic
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 1234567890 +-=/ £\$%&(){}|![]?^*~@#

Montserrat Light Italic
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 1234567890 +-=/ £\$%&(){}|![]?^*~@#

Montserrat Regular Italic
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 1234567890 +-=/ £\$%&(){}|![]?^*~@#

Montserrat Medium Italic
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 1234567890 +-=/ £\$%&(){}|![]?^*~@#

Montserrat SemiBold Italic
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 1234567890 +-=/ £\$%&(){}|![]?^*~@#

Montserrat Bold Italic
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 1234567890 +-=/ £\$%&(){}|![]?^*~@#

Montserrat ExtraBold Italic
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 1234567890 +-=/ £\$%&(){}|![]?^*~@#

Montserrat Black Italic
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 1234567890 +-=/ £\$%&(){}|![]?^*~@#

Secondary font

It is possible to use a secondary font for "crops" to facilitate compatibility with all platforms and devices **only in cases where the institutional font cannot be used** (for example, for memos, email text, papers, etc.).

The secondary typeface is:

Arial font family
 (installed on every device)

Arial Regular
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 1234567890 +-=/ £\$%&(){}|![]?^*~@#

Arial Bold
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 1234567890 +-=/ £\$%&(){}|![]?^*~@#

Arial Italic Regular
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 1234567890 +-=/ £\$%&(){}|![]?^*~@#

Arial Italic Bold
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 1234567890 +-=/ £\$%&(){}|![]?^*~@#

8.1.7. Improper use of the logo

Unauthorized variations

In order to maintain the logo's recognizability and consistency with the brand image, it is necessary to adhere to these logo usage guidelines and not modify its colors, fonts, arrangement of elements, etc., as shown in the following examples.

Do not stretch the logo either vertically or horizontally.

Do not alter the proportion and position of the text elements among themselves.

Unauthorized variations

Do not change the logo font.

Do not change the logo colors.

Unauthorized variations

Do not use the logo in outline.

Do not modify, delete, or change individual elements.

Unauthorized variations

Do not apply shadows, gradients, or other effects.

Do not apply the brand on images or graphics that compromise its readability.

8.1.8. Visual identity

Digital screen application

Alongside images with applied visual identity suggestions and examples of logo applications on mobile and desktop screens.

35

Graphics and tables application

Graphs and tables must be in line with the visual identity and must necessarily follow the same style presented here: monochrome, solid, and rounded geometric shapes.

The colors must necessarily be those of the primary or secondary palette.

The font must be Montserrat; if it is not possible to use the primary font, Arial may be used as the secondary font.

Iconographic style

Icons must align with the visual identity and must necessarily follow the same style presented here: monochrome icons, solid, and with rounded shapes.

The colors must necessarily be those of the primary or secondary palette. If the color "Green" is to be used for the icons, they must be placed on dark backgrounds.

Examples have been provided on the side for inspiration.

